

Project information

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Document information

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Table of contents

Project information	1
Deliverable information	1
Document information.....	1
LEAPS-INNOV 4 th Annual Meeting Description	2
Annex 1 - 4 th LEAPS-INNOV Annual Meeting agenda	6

4th Annual LEAPS-INNOV Annual Meeting Group picture, 18 February 2025

LEAPS-INNOV 4th Annual Meeting Description

The 4th LEAPS-INNOV Annual Meeting was held as a hybrid meeting on 17-19 February 2025 at Area Science Park, Trieste, Italy hosted by Elettra with 115 registered participants.

The participants of the meeting consisted mostly of LEAPS-INNOV members; 98 persons attended in person, 17 participated remotely in the meeting. The beneficiaries were represented by participants from all project beneficiaries, the WP leaders and WP members, as well as members of the

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Governing Board, members of the LEAPS working and strategy groups, two members of the Innovation Advisory Board and the current chair of LEAPS Jakub Szlachetko.

The annual meeting provided the opportunity for all LEAPS-INNOV partners to meet and engage in active discussions fostering the exchange within the project and to dive further into the very constructive working atmosphere in the project.

The meeting started on Monday, 17 February in the afternoon with the opportunity for a networking lunch followed by work package (WP) meetings for WP 3, 5, 7 and 8.

WP2 decided to have their next WP meeting independently of the annual meeting due to testing of the prototypes developed in the last months, which required the presence of some researchers working in the WP. WP 8 used this opportunity of a free time slot to have two dedicated sessions during this annual meeting. Therefore, WP 4, 6, 8 and 9 met (again) in the morning of 18 February. Highly desired tours to Elettra were offered parallel to the WP meetings to those participants whose WP meeting was not taking place at this time. The tours offered the possibility to get to know the operations and technologies of Elettra at a closer look. All WP meetings were well attended and offered the opportunity for remote participation. The meetings were used by the WPs to exchange about the most recent progress, to plan the steps for the remaining project months and to start wrapping up their results. The outcomes of the meetings were shown in the plenary session.

Eva Gimenez-Navarro (LEAPS-INNOV WP2 leader) and Ray Barrett (LEAPS-INNOV WP3 leader) presenting the progress in their work packages.

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The plenary session started after the lunch break of the second day with a warm welcome by Maya Kiskinova (Elettra) followed by an introduction by the scientific project leader Elke Plönjes-Palm (DESY). She gave an overview talk of the progress in LEAPS-INNOV in the last year and presented the work to be done in the remaining seven months of the project and the timeline for the final reporting process.

Maya Kiskinova (Elettra) and Elke Plönjes (scientific project leader, DESY) opening the 4th LEAPS-INNOV Annual Meeting plenary session.

The plenary session, that could be attended also remotely, was continued by talks by the WP leaders. Starting with WP2 all work packages except for the management work package gave a 20-minute presentation followed by a Q&A session after each talk. The WP leaders used this opportunity to show the impressive work and achievements of the last year, but presented also challenges and how they overcame them or plan to tackle them in the next months. It became once again very clear that the granted project extension was deeply required and allows the WPs to achieve their aimed for developments. This part of the plenary session closed with talks by Cristina Modolo on “Industry engagement in technical WPs” and Nuria Valls on “SME engagement in TamaTA”. The second day ended with a working dinner, which further strengthened the connections and constructive atmosphere within the consortium.

The third and last day began with the Governing Board meeting followed by the last part of the plenary session. It started with a general presentation on the status and progress of WP9. Afterwards the co-creation projects, funded within WP9, had the opportunity to present their findings and achievements.

The project coordinators had prepared a 45-minute interactive feedback session, embedded in the plenary using the tool Mentimeter. The session allowed to give anonymous feedback on the core topics of the project and lessons learned for future projects as well as the option to ask questions, comment and to open an in-person discussion in the room and with the remote participants.

The Innovation Advisory Board had a dedicated meeting with the LEAPS chairs at the last LEAPS Plenary in October 2024. The IAB used their time at this LEAPS-INNOV Annual Meeting to report from the meeting at the LEAPS Plenary. They gave insights in their view on the LEAPS-INNOV project and elaborated which further steps are needed to foster the collaboration of LEAPS and LEAPS-INNOV with industry. This highly informative and valued insights were followed by a presentation by Jakub Szlachetko, LEAPS chair, who informed about the LEAPS strategy for 2025 and beyond.

Impressions from the 4th LEAPS-INNOV Annual Meeting

Like in the previous years, the annual meeting aimed at fostering the exchange within the project and to bring together the LEAPS-INNOV consortium. The meeting offered the possibility not only to exchange and engage within, but also across the work packages which was highly valued by the attendees and the important topics were discussed lively at the meeting.

The impressive and highly informative presentations in the plenary session, the WP meetings and the networking opportunities led to a lively exchange between all participants. The meeting was found to be very successful by the organisers and attendees and offered a perfect opportunity to usher in the final project months.

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Annex 1 - 4th LEAPS-INNOV Annual Meeting agenda

LEAPS-INNOV: Annual Meeting 2025
Agenda
17 – 19 February 2025
Elettra and Area Science Park, Trieste

Event website:

<https://indico.elettra.eu/event/49/>

Zoom link for the plenary sessions:

Tuesday, 18 February, 13:30 - 18:30

Wednesday ,19 February, 08:00-13:30

Monday February 17, 2025 (Area Science Park, Elettra), 13:00-18:30 CET

- 13:00 Registration & Networking Lunch (*Area Science Park*)
- 14:00 - 18:00 **WP Session 1** (parallel WP meetings)
- 16:00 - 16:30 Coffee Break
- 14:30 -18:00 tour to Elettra parallel to WP meetings

- 19:30 WP dinners (own costs, WP own organization)

Tuesday February 18, 2025 (Area Science Park, Elettra), 08:00-14:00 CET

- 09:00 -12:30 tour to Elettra parallel to WP meetings
- 09:00 - 13:00 **WP Session 2** (parallel WP meetings) (*Area Science Park*)
- 10:00-10:30 Coffee Break

- 13:00 Lunch

- 14:15 Group photo

LEAPS-INNOV PLENARY MEETING (Area Science Park) Tuesday February 18, 2025, 14:00-22:30 CET

14:30 - 18:30 **Plenary Session 1**
Plönjes

chaired by Jakub Szlachetko, Elke

- 14:30 Welcome (10') *Maya Kiskinova*
- 14:40 Introduction by the Coordinator (10') *Elke Plönjes*
- 14:50 – 18:30 Reports from WPs, lessons-learned industry cooperation (20'+5' each)
WP leaders
 - 14:50 WP2 report
 - 15:15 WP3 report
 - 15:40 WP4 report
- **16:05-16:25 Coffee Break**
 - 16:25 WP5 report
 - 16:50 WP6 report
 - 17:15 WP7 report
 - 17:40 WP8 report
 - 18:05 WP8: Industry engagement in technical WPs (10') *Cristina Modolo*
 - 18:15 WP8: SME engagement in TamaTA (10') *Nuria Valls*
- **20:00 Working Dinner**

Wednesday February 19, 2025 (Area Science Park), 08:00-14:30 CET

- 08:00 - 8:45 **GB meeting** (closed session, 45') (*Area Science Park*)
- 09:00 - 10:30 **Plenary Session 2** *chaired by Elizabeth Shotton*
 - Reports from WPs, lessons-learned industry cooperation (20'+5')
 - 9:00 WP9
 - 09:25- 10:10 Reports from co-creation projects (15'+5')
 - 09:25 EASYBRAGG
 - 09:45 STRAQTECH
 - 10:05 AFX
- **10:30 – 11:00 Coffee Break**

- 11:00 – 12:30 **Plenary Session 3** *chaired by Ray Barrett*
 - 11:00 Feedback session (45') *all*
 - 11:45 LEAPS-INNOV IAB presentation (10'+ 5') *Michael Hennig, Peter Anastasi*
 - 12:00 LEAPS Strategy and Priorities in 2025+ (10'+ 5') *Jakub Szlachetko*
 - 12:15 Lessons learned, wrap up and closing remarks (10') *Elke Plönjes*
 - 12:30 joint lunch with RIANA project

13:30 end of meeting

